

TABLE I

Aromatic amine.	Dye obtained.	*Colour of the dye.	M.P.
1. <i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	Monoazo	Yellow	68-69°
2. "	Disazo	Yellowish brown	96-97°
3. 2,5-Dichloroaniline	"	Dark brown	106-107°
4. <i>o</i> -Anisidine	Monoazo	Orange-red	100-101°
5. <i>p</i> -Anisidine	"	Yellowish brown	59-60°
6. <i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	"	Reddish brown	96-97°
7. <i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	"	Yellow	64-65°
8. <i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	"	Orange	80-81°
9. <i>p</i> -Toluidine	Disazo	Brown	85-86°
10. Benzidine	"	Reddish brown (powder).	139-40°
11. Anthranilic acid	Monoazo	Brown	109-10°
12. α -Naphthylamine	"	Orange	76-77°
13. "	Disazo	Dark violet	124-25°
14. β -Naphthylamine	Monoazo	Reddish brown	72-73°
15. "	Disazo	Dark brown	87-88°

*All the dyes are crystalline needles except No. 10.

In the case of monoazo dyes, coupling of the diazonium salt is expected to take place preferentially in 4-position of 3-pentadecylphenol. This point was further experimentally proved by reducing the dyes obtained from *p*-chloroaniline, *o*-anisidine, *p*-nitroaniline, and anthranilic acid with sodium hydrosulphite and isolating 4-amino-3-pentadecylphenol.

It is well known that the *ortho*-hydroxyazo dyes form co-ordinate compounds with metallic atoms, such as chromium, copper, aluminium, etc., by implicating the metal atom in a 6-membered chelate ring⁷⁻⁸. The monoazo dyes did not form copper complexes, thus indicating that these were not *o*-hydroxyazo dyes.

7. Bamberger, *Ber.*, 1900 33, 1951.

8. Drew and Landquist, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 202.

The disazo dyes isolated could be either 2,4- or 4,6-disazophenols. The latter structure (II), however, seems to be more likely as the coupling in 2-position will be comparatively difficult due to steric hindrance.

If the pentadecyl chain in 3-position were not likely to hinder the coupling in 2-position, the formation of 2,4- or 4,6-disazo dye would be equally feasible. If it is so, *p*-xylenol should furnish the 2,4-disazo dye in as much quantity as 3-pentadecylphenol.

Model experiments were carried out with *p*-xylenol, using *p*-toluidine as a coupling component. Only a small quantity (10%) of the disazo dye was formed along with the major quantity (about 90%) of the monoazo dye, whereas *p*-toluidine afforded exclusively a disazo dye on coupling with 3-pentadecylphenol.

TABLE II

S.No.	Amines and its diazotised soln. (in ml).	Phenol in EtOH.	10 <i>N</i> . Aq. NaOH.	**Mono. or bis dye.	†Cryst. form & shape.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline-HCl (0.815 g.); 40 ml	1.52 g. in 60 ml	4 ml	4,6-Bis-(<i>p</i> -chlorobenzene)-AP (0.24 g.)	EtOH X 3; yellowish brown	98-97°	C ₃₃ H ₄₀ ON ₄ Cl ₃	C : 68.29% H : 7.23 N : 9.70	68.30% 7.24 9.66
*2			4	4-(<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzene)-AP (0.06 g.)	80% AcOH (dil.) X 4; yellow	68-69°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl	C : 73.39 H : 8.62 N : 6.35	73.31 8.82 6.34
3	2,5-Dichloroaniline (1.62 g.); 50 ml	3.64 g. in 75 ml	6	4,6-Bis-(2,5-dichlorobenzene)-AP (0.16 g.)	Dil. acetone (95%) X 3; dark brown	106-107° (shrinks at 99°)	C ₃₅ H ₄₀ ON ₄ Cl ₄	C : 61.21 H : 6.34 N : 8.47	61.11 6.17 8.64
4	<i>o</i> -Anilidine (0.62 g.); 35 ml	1.52 g. in 50 ml	4	4-(<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzene)-AP (1.3 g.)	EtOH (dil) X 2; orange-red	100-101°	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	C : 77.02 H : 9.35 N : 6.80	76.66 9.80 6.4
5	<i>p</i> -Anilidine (0.62 g.); 35 ml	1.52 g. in 50 ml	4	4-(<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzene)-AP (0.54 g.)	Dil. AcOH X 3	50-60°	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂	C : 76.88 H : 9.69 N : 6.72	76.66 9.60 6.4
6	<i>o</i> -Nitrosaniline (0.69 g.); 30 ml	1.52 g. in 45 ml	4	4-(<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzene)-AP (0.7 g.)	EtOH X 2; reddish brown	98-97°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃	C : 71.30 H : 8.60 N : 9.50	71.52 8.61 9.27
7	<i>m</i> -Nitrosaniline (0.69 g.); 30 ml	1.52 g. in 40 ml	4	4-(<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzene)-AP (0.17 g.)	Dil. AcOH (95%) X 3; yellow	64-65°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃	C : 71.38 H : 8.54 N : 9.30	71.52 8.61 9.27
8	<i>p</i> -Nitrosaniline (0.69 g.); 30 ml	1.52 g. in 45 ml	4	4-(<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzene)-AP (0.8 g.)	EtOH X 2; orange	80-81°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃	C : 71.5 H : 8.40 N : 9.05	71.52 8.61 9.27
9	<i>p</i> -Toluidine (1.07 g.); 40 ml	3.04 g. in 60 ml	6	4,6-Bis-(<i>p</i> -Tolyl)-AP (0.50 g.)	Dil. EtOH (80%) X 3; brown	85-86°	C ₃₅ H ₄₀ ON ₄	C : 77.79 H : 8.62 N : 10.53	77.73 8.95 10.36

TABLE II (contd.)

S. No.	Amine and diazotised soln. (in ml).	Phenol in EtOH.	10N-NaOH. **Mono- or bis dye.	‡Cryat. form & shape.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
10	Benzidine (0.92 g.); 40 ml	3.04 g. in 60 ml	4,4'-Bis-(2-penta-decyl-4-hydroxy-benzene)-azo-diphenyl (0.72 g.)	Dil. Et OH; reddish brown	139-40°	C ₃₄ H ₇₈ O ₂ N ₄	C : 70.05% H : 9.20 N : 7.30	79.60 9.60 6.90
11	Anthranilic acid (0.69 g.); 30 ml	1.52 g. in 45 ml	4-(o-Carboxybenzene)-AP (0.72 g.)	Do X2; dark brown	109-10°	C ₂₈ H ₄₀ O ₃ N ₂	C : 74.57 H : 8.70 N : 6.26	74.3 8.85 6.19
12	α-Naphthylamine (0.715 g.); 30 ml	1.52 g. in 45 ml	4,6-Bis-(1-naphthyl)-AP (0.04 g.)	Gl. AcOH X3; dark violet	124-25°	C ₄₁ H ₄₈ ON ₄	C : 80.38 H : 7.95 N : 9.20	80.35 7.90 9.14
13*	" "	" "	4-(1-Naphthyl)-AP (0.25 g.)	Dil. AcOH (80%) X3; orange	76-77°	C ₃₁ H ₄₂ ON ₂	C : 81.3 H : 9.40 N : 6.50	81.18 9.23 6.11
14	β-Naphthylamine (0.715 g.); 30 ml	1.52 g in 45 ml	4,6-Bis-(2-naphthyl)-AP (0.1g.)	Gl. AcOH X3; dark brown	87-88°	C ₄₁ H ₄₈ ON ₄	C : 80.52 H : 8.30 N : 8.90	80.35 7.90 9.14
15*	" "	" "	4-(2-Naphthyl)-AP (0.07 g.)	Dil AcOH; reddish brown	72-73°	C ₃₁ H ₄₂ ON ₂	C : 81.54 H : 9.40 N : 6.39	81.18 8.23 6.11
16	p-Toluidine (1.07 g.); 40 ml	p-Xylenol (1.22 g.) in 40 ml	2,4-Bis-(p-Tolulyl)-azo-3,6-xyloene-1-ol (0.1 g.).	Gl. AcOH; chocolate	200-201°	C ₆₈ H ₈₂ ON ₄	C : 73.48 H : 5.80 N : 15.40	73.74 6.14 15.64
17*	" "	" "	4-(p-Tolulyl)-azo-3,6-xyloene-1-ol (1.24 g.)	Dil. AcOH X 2 (70%); yellow	111-13°	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ ON ₂	C : 75.33 H : 7.00 N : 11.42	75.00 6.66 11.66

*Monoazo dyes marked with asterisk were isolated from mother liquors of bis-dyes.

**Yield in parentheses

‡All the dyes except No. 10 crystallised in needles.

N. B. AP denotes -azo-3-pentadecylphenol. 3-Phentadecylphenol was used in all cases except otherwise mentioned.

The above results definitely show that the coupling in 2-position is hindered. Thus although the ambiguity regarding the structure of the disazo dyes of 3-pentadecylphenol cannot be said as unequivocally settled, it can be reasonably assumed that the disazo dyes are 4,6-disazo isomers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The aromatic amines were diazotised using sodium nitrite and the diazonium salts were coupled with 3-pentadecylphenol, dissolved in ethanolic alkali. The dyes were precipitated by acidification and crystallised from suitable solvents. Equimolecular quantities of the amine, sodium nitrite, and phenol were used, with the exception of benzidine where two moles of the phenol and sodium nitrite were used for a mole of benzidine. The quantities of the amine and phenol used and the physical constants and analyses of the dyes isolated are recorded in Table II.

Reduction of 4-(p-Chlorobenzene)azo-3-pentadecylphenol.—To a solution of the dye (0.11 g.) in ethanol (20 ml) containing 0.5% aqueous potassium hydroxide (5 ml) was added aqueous sodium hydrosulphite at 65-75° till the red solution turned pale tan, indicating complete reduction. A few drops of dilute acetic acid were added and the solution was cooled to 0°. The tan-coloured precipitate was filtered and dried in vacuum; yield 0.08 g. It was crystallised from hexane in cream-coloured needles, m.p. 105-106° (lit. m.p. 105.5-106.5°). It turned grey on exposure; yield 0.055 g. (Found: C, 78.75; H, 11.46; N, 4.17. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{37}ON$: C, 79.00; H, 11.60; N, 4.39%).

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